

DETECTION FREQUENCY OF GROUP P ANTIGENS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PHARYNGITIS.

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Аннотация. Проблемы, связанные с хроническими инфекционно-воспалительными, иммунопатологическими поражениями носоглотки у детей до настоящего времени продолжают сохранять свою чрезвычайную актуальность. Исследовать частоту присутствия в крови больных хроническом фарингитом (ХФ) иммуноантигена P₁ во взаимосвязи с клиническими особенностями хронических воспалительных заболеваний носоглотки. Изучено состояние антигена P₁ сыворотке крови, 192 ребенка больных хроническим фарингитом. Полученные данные позволяют утверждать о частоте проявлений антигенов P у здоровых детей и больных ХФ в значительной степени дифференцировано.

Ключевые слова: хроническом фарингит, иммуноантиген P, фенотип, носоглотка, маркер.

Abstract. Problems associated with chronic infectious and inflammatory, immunopathological lesions of the nasopharynx in children continue to retain their extreme relevance to this day. To study the frequency of the presence of immunoantigen P1 in the blood of patients with chronic pharyngitis (CP) in relation to the clinical features of chronic inflammatory diseases of the nasopharynx. The state of the P1 antigen in the blood serum of 192 children with chronic pharyngitis was studied. The data obtained allow us to state that the frequency of manifestations of P antigens in healthy children and patients with CP is significantly differentiated.

Keywords: chronic pharyngitis, immunoantigen P, phenotype, nasopharynx, marker.

Аннотация. Болаларда бурун-халқумнинг сурункали юқумли-яллигланишли, иммунопатологик жарёнлари билан боғлиқ муаммолар бугунги кунгача жуда долзарб бўлиб қолмоқда. Бурун-халқумнинг сурункали яллигланиши касалликларининг клиник хусусиятлари билан боғлиқ ҳолда сурункали фарингит (СФ) билан оғриган беморларнинг қонида P₁ иммуноантигенининг мавжудлигини ўрганиш. Қон зардобидаги P₁ антигенининг ҳолати сурункали фарингит билан оғриган 192 болада ўрганилди. Сурункали фарингит билан касалланган 192 та боланинг қон зардобида P₁ антигенининг ҳолати ўрганилди. Олинган маълумотлар соғлом болаларда ва СФ билан оғриган беморларда P₁ антигенларининг намоён бўлиши частотаси сезиларли даражада фарқланишини таъкидлаш имконини беради.

Калим сўзлар: сурункали фарингит, иммуноантиген P₁, фенотип, бурун-халқум, маркер.

Problems associated with chronic infectious and inflammatory, immunopathological lesions of the nasopharynx in children continue to be extremely relevant to this day [2,3]. This situation is true despite the significant progress achieved in recent years in understanding the etiopathogenetic and clinical patterns of this pathology in childhood. All this has made it possible to expand the possibility of preventing and treating chronic inflammatory processes of the lymphoid ring of the nasopharynx. At the same time, this pathology still remains significant in frequency and prevalence in childhood. Chronic pharyngitis still plays a significant role in the

implementation of a wide range of diseases of other organs and systems [1,4]. In this case, the leading place is occupied by diseases of the bronchopulmonary, cardiovascular and urinary systems. A number of clinical manifestations of the vegetative-visceral dysfunction syndrome in children are associated with the anatomical and physiological features of the lymphoid ring of the nasopharynx. That is, solutions to the problems of chronic lymphoid inflammatory-hyperplastic reactions must be sought from the standpoint of systemic analysis, including various levels - metabolic, constitutional-genetic, geneological [5,6].

Objective of the study: To investigate the frequency of presence of immunoantigen P1 in the blood of patients with chronic pharyngitis (CP) in relation to the clinical features of chronic inflammatory diseases of the nasopharynx.

Materials and methods. Clinical observations and special examinations of 192 children aged 4 to 14 years with chronic phrenia were conducted. The study was conducted at the pediatric clinic of TashPMI. Of the total number of patients, 87 boys and 105 girls were examined. Based on the data of organizational and methodological aspects, the indicated higher sexual differentiation among patients with chronic phrenia can be considered natural for the region of Uzbekistan. This is quite consistent with medical and biological concepts, according to which the phenomena of lymphatism and all the ensuing consequences in genetic and phenotypic terms are more acceptable for the female body, which was revealed in the higher frequency of manifestations of chronic phrenia according to the results of this work among girls. The control group consisted of 71 children of the same age. All children upon admission underwent a study of the morphology of peripheral blood and ESR, urine sediment analysis, and the presence of C-reactive protein in the blood was also studied. Determination of the P1 antigen in blood serum using diagnostic anti-P1 goat serum (produced by the St. Petersburg Research Institute of Vaccines and Sera of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation) in liquid blood, in a saline medium at a temperature of +4-6.

Results and discussion. One of the antigen structures of erythrocytes that has immunogenetic prerequisites is the P antigen. The results of studies of the frequency of occurrence of the P antigen in patients with CP and healthy children based on our studies are presented in the table

Table

Frequency of distribution of P1 antigen in patients with chronic pharyngitis depending on the gender of the subjects.

Antigen types	Frequency of analyzed features in %				P
	In healthy children		Patients with CP		
	boys	girls	boys	girls	
P ₁ (+)	56,3 %	56,5 %	31,1 %	30,4 %	P ₁ < 0,02
P (-)	43,7 %	43,5 %	68,9 %	69,6 %	P ₂ < 0,01

As follows from the presented data, the ratio of antigen P in healthy children and patients with CP is significantly differentiated. Thus, in particular, among healthy children not prone to chronic inflammatory diseases of the nasopharynx and regardless of gender, the frequency of P1 (+) antigens dominates. While in patients with CP, there is a complete inversion, namely, the prevalence of the occurrence of antigen P (-).

Thus, as follows from the obtained data, the formation of chronic inflammatory diseases of the lymphoid tissue of the nasopharynx is basically not a random factor, but a genetically determined phenotypic marker of the analyzed conditions and, in particular, on the model of chronic pharyngitis. Although, of course, other contributing factors can also have their regulatory effect. However, their result as a whole is outlined in the above-mentioned pattern, namely, healthy children are characterized by the prevalence of P1 (+) antigen, and patients with chronic pharyngitis P (-) antigen. Among the above-mentioned contributing factors that can influence individual fluctuations in the frequency of realization of the P1 antigen, the inbreeding factor in the genealogy of probands can be of some importance to a certain extent.

Conclusions

Chronic inflammatory diseases of the lymphoid tissue of the nasopharynx are not a random factor, but a genetically determined phenotypic marker of the analyzed conditions and, in particular, on the model of chronic pharyngitis.

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